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This is to certify that the research paper entitled “Technology-Driven Transformation of Physical Education and Sports: Implications for Teaching, Coaching, and Athlete Development”, authored by “Saini, Dr. Ankur Singh”, has been successfully published in ADEJ, Volume – 3, Issue – 2 (April-June 2026).

The paper has been assigned the DOI link: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19674140>

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